

THE STATE OF SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRIAL CLUSTERS

A.A.Sobirov

**Associate Professor of Marketing Department of Tashkent State University
of Economics**

Email: a.sobirov@tsue.uz

Annotation: The effective implementation of a cluster development strategy is a factor in ensuring economic growth and increasing the competitiveness of the regional economy and the country as a whole due to the effects of: division of labor, scale, savings on transaction costs, free information exchange, technology transfer, as well as the synergy effect. The economic integration of enterprises within cluster structures is aimed, among other things, at innovative development and opens up opportunities for technological breakthroughs, in accordance with the main directions of the Strategy for Scientific and Technological Development. work examines current issues of the formation and development of Russian innovative industrial clusters. A comparative description of economic growth factors in the 5th and 6th technological structures is presented. The fragmentary aspects of cluster theory are considered, the features of economic development models within the framework of traditional and cluster approaches are outlined. In the context of the innovative component of development, the mission of clusters is related to the production of innovations: from fundamental ideas to commercialization of projects and active expansion into the field of practical use. The main factors for the development of an innovative industrial cluster are detailed and classified. An analysis of the effectiveness of the functioning of innovation clusters in the context of large-scale support of government

development programs was carried out. As a result of the study, the author concluded about the importance of the practical implementation of the stated measures to stimulate the technological component of economic growth at the national and regional levels.

Key words: innovative industrial cluster, innovative development, cluster strategy, competitiveness, sustainable development, economic efficiency.

In the context of global political and economic instability, restrictive measures and sanctions regime in relation to sectors of the national economy, there is an objective need for Russia to transition to an innovative type of development, an integral part of which is neo-industrialization, the use of new mechanisms to increase the competitiveness of industries in the manufacturing sector and the qualitative transformation of the productive forces. The rate of economic growth in the long term will directly depend on scientific and technological progress and the reproduction of innovative potential.

In the period of globalization and consolidation, markets lead to the creation of cluster systems; the implementation of replacement cluster potential leads to a strategy for directing the growth of the competitiveness of regional economic entities, based on the principles of institutional and cost approaches. In conditions of crisis economic needs, the need to develop the economy of the country, its remote regions and industries is an important and pressing problem. Achieving and solving these problems can be based on a cluster approach to innovative development of regions, which stimulates the development and ensuring the competitiveness of territories. The modern scientific direction is controversial, as evidenced by many studies by economists.

In the scientific aspect, the theory of cluster development represents the concepts of the synthesis of advertising production and the competitive advantages of the company, which entails the emergence of cluster formations in various industry regions under the influence of two groups factor: external and internal. The

concept of development of economic regions based on clusters ensures consistent interaction between the public sector and the economics of commercial sectors, stimulating income growth, the creation of new jobs in the zones, and a constant quality of life for the population (the highest level of average wages in the regions, using the example of the Central Federal District).

In modern market conditions, clusters represent a modern type of territorial organization of regional markets operating on vertically integrated structures, which involves providing an alternative way to create a value chain. On the one hand, clusters act as associations of the production and social spheres, on the other hand, they implement the strategy of regional industrial development. An industrial regional cluster is a geographically defined dependence of interdependent enterprises and organizations with intensive sales resources, ensuring their close interaction, which allows maximizing common opportunities and minimizing risks. The dynamic innovative development of regional enterprises and organizations - cluster participants - is a key factor in ensuring a positive synergy effect.

Innovation processes and projects represent a more structural system of interacting elements that provide a high return on capital. The process of emergence and implementation of the region's innovative development strategy includes the following stages:

- determining the goals of the innovation strategy for the development of the region;
- Conducting an analysis of the region's innovative activities;
- development and implementation of the Concept, implementing the text of the innovative development of the region;
- implementation of the strategy for innovative development of the region. In modern market conditions, the cluster approach as an information resource is used to build the Concept of the strategic development of the region, providing data on

the state of the real sector of the region's economy, priority areas for industrial development, which leads to an increase in the innovative potential of the region as a whole.

The following fundamental prerequisites serve as special justifications and implementation of cluster policy on the territory:

- activity of territorial production complexes (TPC) until the 1990s;
- the current existence of federal target programs for the development of economic sectors, the construction of independent (special) economic zones on the territory of clusters;
- innovative direction of development of enterprises participating in clusters in the chemical, pharmaceutical and mechanical engineering industries;
 - a large number of research and design institutes within the military-industrial complexes, currently specializing in the field of aviation, petrochemical and military-industrial production.

On the one hand, an innovation regional cluster is a separate geographical concentration of industrial enterprises united by a single research system of institutions and forming technological, logistics and infrastructure chains, based on the simultaneous use of various market mechanisms: cooperation and competition, which leads to the effective dissemination of information . On the other hand, regional innovation-oriented economic clusters act as a tool for implementing economic policy, combining the activation of market mechanisms and the use of the potential effects of state participation in the implementation of complex socio-economic solutions. Considering the activities of these clusters in the territories of federal districts, it is possible to trace positive trends in the development of these regions when studying the dependencies between the scope of the region's research potential (R&D costs, technological innovations) and the level of innovative products in the total volume of output in the regions in which the following are located innovation clusters.

—increasing the share of innovative goods, works and services in the total sales revenue of enterprises participating in the cluster;

— an increase in the share of gross profit in revenue from sales of enterprises participating in the cluster as a result of the introduction of R&D results into the production process;

—increasing the share of organizations in the field of R&D in the total number of participants in the innovation cluster.

An innovative regional cluster is a system of geographically adjacent interconnected industrial enterprises and organizations that complement each other on the basis of the formation of a unified strategy of corporate governance and cooperation, as a result of the interaction of which the presentation of the innovative potential of cluster participants increases their competitive advantages, which, in particular, is expressed in the creation additional economic added value and leads to an increase in the value of companies and their investment attractiveness.

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